

Career Maturity as Correlates of Job Involvement Among Secondary School Teachers in Anambra State

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between career maturity and job involvement of secondary school teachers in Anambra State. Two research questions and one hypothesis guided the study. The study adopted correlational research design. Population was all the teachers in the government owned secondary schools in Anambra State. A sample size of 605 teachers were drawn from 30 secondary schools in the six education zone through multi-stage procedure. Instrument for data collection were career maturity inventory and job involvement scale. Data analysis was done using the returned 591 questionnaire correctly filled by the respondents. Research questions 1 – 2 were answered using summed scores while the hypothesis was tested using t-test of correlation. The result of the study indicates that the teachers have low career maturity but high job involvement. It also revealed negligible negative relationship between career maturity and job involvement. Based on the findings, implications of the study were noted. Recommendations were made which include regular supervision of the teachers and reward of highly involved teachers.

Key words: Teacher, Career Maturity, Job Involvement

Introduction

The realization of the goals of secondary school education in Nigeria including Anambra State partly lies in the hands of teachers. The teacher is the central figure in any educational programme and the medium by which the subject of learning is presented to the students. Abiogu (2014) noted that the teacher is of great importance in the success or failure of any innovation in education while Atanda and Lamed (2006) regarded the teacher as a professional who imparts skill, knowledge, information and attitude among others to the learner. The teacher is the anchor for the effective functioning of educational system and for the improvement of the learning process. Without the effort of the teacher, the whole of the education and policy process will

remain "a jig-saw puzzle whose bits and pieces hang together in a crazy quilt" (Abiogu, 2014). A teacher cannot achieve such feat without having high career maturity.

Salami (2008) defined career maturity as the extent to which the individual has mastered the vocational development task including both knowledge and attitudinal components appropriate to his or her state of career development. Maturity is assumed to be an underlying psychological construct reflecting this developmental level just as intellectual, moral and social development are assumed to be psychological construct. As a construct, career maturity, represents a repertoire of coping behaviours and one's readiness to employ these behaviours toward career related events encountered at various life stages. According to Salami (2008), the highlighted aspects of career maturity include: (i) obtaining information about oneself and converting such information to self knowledge, (ii) acquiring decision-making skills and applying them in effective decision making, (iii) gathering career information and converting it into knowledge of the occupational world, integrating self— knowledge and knowledge of the occupational world; (iv) and implementing the obtained knowledge in career planning.

Career maturity is central to a developmental approach to understanding vocational behaviour and involves an assessment of an individual's level of career progress in relation to his or her career-relevant development tasks. It refers broadly to the individual's readiness to make informed age appropriate career decision and cope with career development tasks (Sirohi, 2013). Looking at model of career maturity from the angles of affective and cognitive dimension Sirohi (2013) posited that, while the cognitive dimension is composed of decision making skills, the affective include attitudes toward the career decision making process. Also, focusing on the cognitive dimension, Coetzee and Jacobs (2007) were of the view that career maturity refers to a person's ability to make career decisions that reflect decisiveness, self-reliance, independence and a willingness to compromise between personal needs and requirements of one's career situation. The construct of career maturity consists of a readiness, attitude and competency to cope effectively with the career development tasks. The assumption can be made that career matured individuals have the ability to achieve their goals. Career maturity is thus the degree that one has reached in cognitive, emotional and other psychological factors whereby one acquires the capacity to make realistic and mature decisions.

It is also important that managers of any organization put into consideration the way employees view their job and address the challenges during the recruitment process. The level at which the employee values the job may affect the level of his/her involvement when recruited. In other words, it is important that the employees of labour implement strategies that will increase job involvement.

According to Kanugo (1982), job involvement referred to as psychological identification with a job. This implies that a job-involved person sees his/her job as an important part of his or her self-concept and that jobs define one's self concept in a major way. Ingram, Lee and Lucas (1991) opined that job involvement (or lack of it) has been clearly linked to absenteeism. They noted that if one has high job involvement, the job becomes part of one's identity and is more likely to cross

situational boundaries thereby reducing segmentation of the job role and increasing inter role conflict.

Saks (2006) described job involvement as the strict cognitive evaluation of one's job and how it pertains to whom that person is as an individual. He also noted that highly job involved individuals make the job a central part of their personal character.

Omoniyi and Adedapo (2012) defined job involvement as the degree to which an employee is engaged in and enthusiastic about performing his/her job. It describes the process of internalizing the importance of a work based on an individual formed opinion about one's career and it depicts a function of the level of satisfaction which an individual can derive on it by helping to meet certain desires. Highly job involved individuals make the job a central part of their personal character. Aderibigbe, Igboanusi, and Gwaison (2014) described job involvement as the process of internalizing the importance of a work, based on individual employee. It explains the process involved with which an employee can be more orientated about an organization. Also, it is an attitude formed about one's career and it depicts a function of the level of satisfaction which an individual can derive on it by helping to meet certain desires. Highly involved individuals make the job a central part of their personal character.

Alireza, Hossein, Mohsen and Majid (2015) also noted that job involvement is a subjective condition that makes people devoted to their work. Job involvement is the degree to which a person identifies with his or her job, actively participate in it, and considers his or her performance to self-worth.

In their study, Sethi and Mittal (2016) defined job involvement as an employee's job related significant behaviour. It shows the degree to which an individual is personally involved with his/her job. They further stated that job involvement is one's motivated orientation to the job in which they are engaged. An individual having high involvement would consider their work to be a very important part of their lives and their happiness depend on how they perform their job. Those people who are high in job involvement truly care for and are concerned about their work.

The role of the teacher in the achievement of the educational goals in Nigeria, makes his involvement very important. This is because the entire system will collapse if the teacher is not effective and committed in his duties. The quality of educational process and its products is unquestionably affected by the teachers' job involvement. It therefore implies that effective job involvement of teachers is a must for educational improvement which the nation through the Ministry of Education is working hard to achieve.

For effective planning, development and implementation of the secondary school curriculum, the teacher must be effectively involved and committed to the job. Apart from the knowledge of the subject matter, the teacher must trust him or herself in his or her potentials (self efficacy) for the achievement of the required goals in the education.

In the light of the situation presented above, this study is designed to find out whether career maturity is a correlates of job involvement of the secondary school teachers in Anambra State. From the researcher's observation, it seems that the measurement of the teachers' job involvement has always been judged by the academic achievement of their students. This therefore justifies the need to establish if there is any relationship between career maturity and job involvement of secondary school teachers in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

The teacher is the central figure in the achievement of any education goal. For a positive academic and moral development of the students, the teacher must have good knowledge of his/her subject, possess adequate skill, competence, confidence and right attitude in the discharge of his/her duties. Despite the fact that all the teachers in the state owned secondary school in Anambra State are professionally trained with minimum qualification of Bachelor in Education, there is still evidence of poor academic performance, truancy and dropping out of school among the students. The teachers seem not to be worried by this current development as some of them are seen attending to private business during the school period thereby negating their core duties. This is a worrisome issue that has been a source of concern to other stakeholders in education such as parents, counsellors, school administrators and researchers. It is therefore the focus of this paper to investigate the relationship between career maturity and job involvement of the secondary school teachers in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate if career maturity is a correlate of job involvement among secondary school teachers in Anambra State. Specifically, the study determined the;

1. career maturity scores of secondary school teachers in Anambra State.
2. job involvement scores of the secondary school teachers in Anambra State
3. relationship between the career maturity scores and job involvement scores of secondary school teachers in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study;

1. What are the career maturity scores of the secondary school teachers in Anambra State?
2. What are the job involvement scores of secondary school teachers in Anambra State?
3. What is the relationship between career maturity and job involvement of secondary school teachers in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between career maturity and job involvement of secondary school teachers in Anambra State.

Method

The study adopted a correlational research design. Mukaka (2012) defined correlation as a statistical method used to assess a possible linear association between two continuous variables. The population for the study consists of all the secondary school teachers in Anambra State. The sample size of 605 teachers were drawn from 30 state owned secondary schools using multi-stage sampling procedure. Two instruments – career Maturity Inventory (CMI) and Job Involvement Scale (JIS) were used for data collection. The career maturity inventory contained 24 items while job involvement contains 20 items. The items were rated on four-point scale of “strongly agree”, “agree”, “disagree” and “strongly disagree” with corresponding scale of 4, 3, 2, 1 with 4 points as the highest obtained point and 1 point as the lowest obtained point. The negative statements were reverse coded. The content validity of the instrument as adapted by the researcher was ascertained by two lectures, one from Department of Guidance and Counselling and one from Measurement and Evaluation of Nnamdi Azikiwe University. The content validity of career maturity was obtained using cronbach alpha coefficient yielded 0.70. the coefficence of test re-test reliability obtained by Lodani and Kejner (1965) and adopted by Omoluabi (1997) was used in job involvement lower scores indicate higher job involvement, the data obtained were analyzed using summated scores to answer the research questions while the hypothesis was tested using t-test of correlation.

Result

Research Question 1-2: What are the career maturity scores, and job involvement scores of secondary school teachers in Anambra State?

Table 1. Range of scores of teachers' career maturity

Variables	Range of Scores	N	%	Remark
Career Maturity	38 – 59	328	55.5	Low career maturity
	60 – 90	263	44.5	High career maturity

Table 1 shows that 328 (55.5%) of the teachers with scores ranging from 38-59 have low career maturity, while 263 (44.5%) others with range of scores from 60-90 have high career maturity.

Table 2. Range of scores of teachers' job involvement.

Variables	Range of Scores	N	%	Remark
Job Involvement	38-49	105	17.8	Low job involvement
	50 – 74	486	82.2	High job involvement

Table 2 shows that 105 (17.8%) teachers with scores between 38-49 have low job involvement, while 486 (82.2%) others with range of scores from 50-74 have high job involvement.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between career maturity and job involvement of secondary school teachers in Anambra State?

Table 3: Pearson's Correlation between teachers' career maturity and job involvement

Variables	N	Career Maturity	Job Involvement	Remark
Career Maturity	591	1	-0.070	Negligible Negative Relationship
Job Involvement	591	-0.070	1	

Table 3 shows that there is a negligible negative relationship between career maturity and job involvement of secondary school teachers in Anambra State. This is indicated by the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient, $r(519) = -.070$.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between career maturity and job involvement of secondary school teachers in Anambra State.

Table 4: t-test of significance of relationship between career maturity and job involvement.

Variable	N	Career Maturity	Job Involvement	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Career Maturity	591	1	-0.070	1.70	1.96	Not Significant
Job Involvement	591	-0.070	1			

The analysis in Table 4 shows that at 0.05 level of significance the t-cal value of 1.70 is less than the critical value of 1.96. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between career maturity and job involvement of secondary school teachers in Anambra State. The null hypothesis was not rejected.

Discussion

Relationship between Career Maturity and Job Involvement of Secondary School Teachers in Anambra State

The result of the study revealed that a greater percentage of secondary school teachers in Anambra State have low career maturity. This implies that a greater number of the teachers do not exhibit adequate mastery of knowledge and attitudinal components appropriate for teaching profession. Many factors could be responsible for this. It could be as a result that those teachers did not have interest in the teaching job but forced into it by circumstances such as not having the required qualification to pursue their dream profession.

It could also be as a result of lack of adequate training and continuous retraining to cope with the job demands and challenges. The effect of this state of low career maturity of the teachers is often times manifested in the outcome of learning process. The teacher is regarded as the anchor for effective teaching and learning process. Hence, a teacher with low career maturity will not be in the best position to impact skills, knowledge, information and attitudes among others to the learners as noted by Atanda and Lamed (2006). This has resulted in the continuous record of poor academic achievement and increased rate of truancy among the students.

The study also indicated negligible negative relationship between career maturity and job involvement of the teachers, In other words, the study implies that other factors aside career maturity can improve teachers involvement to their job. Such factors include job satisfaction as a result of regular salaries and other incentives. Satisfied teachers most often put in more efforts to their job in order to achieve better result, This opinion is in line with the findings of Haggling (2005) which revealed significant positive relationship between job satisfaction and job involvement. This is to say that even though the teachers rate themselves as being involved in their jobs, in practice they are not. Their involvement may only be seen when salaries are paid and enough fund in their pockets. However, Houle (2012) in his study noted that employees with high level of career maturity are more involved in their job than those with low career maturity. Also Beheshitifar and Safariyan (2013) noted that high career maturity of employees lead to improvement in productivity. Hence the low career maturity of the teachers as exhibited by the study could be a contributory factors to low academic performance and moral decadence among the secondary school students in Anambra.

Conclusion

The study investigated the relationship between career maturity and job involvement of the secondary school teachers in Anambra State. The result showed that career maturity has negligible relationship with job involvement of teachers. This implies that commitment or involvement is motivated by other factors like salaries and other incentives which further revealed that their absence will show low involvement/commitment by these teachers.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and the implications of the study the following recommendations were made by the researcher;

1. Teachers with high career maturity should be employed to teach in the secondary schools. This is because a career matured person will always put in his/her best considering his/her expertise on the job.
2. There should be regular supervision of the teachers to encourage commitment to duty.
3. Highly committed teachers should be recognized with tangible rewards.

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